

Complexation behaviour of Cd with methylimino diacetic acid (MIDA) and some amino acids at DME

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Complexation behaviour of Cd with methylimino diacetic acid (MIDA) and some amino acids (alanine, glycine, aspartic and glutamic) have been investigated at DME. The formation of MX , MX_2 and MX_2Y complexes has been identified. The reduction of all these complexes has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled, involving two electrons. The treatment of Schaap and McMasters has been used to evaluate the stability constants for all these complexes. The statistical and electrochemical effects have been discussed by using these stability constants. The positive values of mixing constants (K_M) and stabilization constants (K_S) indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes.

Amino acids, which form stable complexes, have analytical importance in separation of transition metals and rare earths¹. A study of these complexes is also important in biological chemistry, in that the accumulation of sufficient data on amino acids complexes with metal ions may contribute to a better understanding of the type of linkages involved in metal protein interactions².

Studies on mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with amino acid and carboxylic acids have been reported by Khan and Nema³⁻⁵. Mixed ligand complexes of Cu, Cd and Pb with different amino acids and malonic acid and oxalic acid has been reported by Shah⁶. Singh *et al.*⁷ has reported mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with phthalate and some amino acids.

Recently, the studies of amino acids have increased due to their wide application. Reduction of glycinate and alaninate complexes of palladium(II) on a dropping mercury electrode at different temperatures has studied kinetically by Nikiforova, Kravtsov and Aleskseeva⁸. The study of the ternary complexes of different metal ions with amino acids and bicarboxylic acids have been carried out in our laboratory⁹⁻¹².

In this communication, it is proposed to undertake comprehensive polarographic studies on the composition and stability of Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate mixed complexes due to the lack of such study.

Results

Simple systems :

The formation constant of the complexes of Cd^{II} with

MIDA, alanine, glycine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid were determined prior to the study of the mixed ligand systems. The stability constants have been evaluated by the method of Deford and Hume as improved by Irving. The plot of $F_0[X]$ vs $[X]$ results into a curve and has an intercept on $F_0[X]$ axis equal to unity in all the systems. The plot of $F_1[X]$ axis give the value equal to β_1 and the plot of $F_2[X]$ vs $[X]$ is a straight line parallel to $[X]$ axis and is independent to $[X]$. Thus all the complexing agents under study in this communication form 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes.

The half wave potential of Cd^{2+} in 0.2 M KNO_3 was measured accurately at the time of running each series of solution and was ranged between -0.579 and -0.583 volt vs SCE.

A simple well-defined reduction wave was obtained in all the cases. The wave was found to be diffusion controlled and reversible. The plot of $E_{d.c.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$ gave a straight line with slope of 30 ± 2 mV.

The results are being summarized in the Table 1. The values agree well with those reported in literature.

Table 1. Stability constants of Cd with MIDA and amino acids

Systems	$\log B_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
Cd-MIDA	5.81	9.05	14.17
Cd-Alaninate	4.24	7.54	9.54
Cd-Glycinate	4.30	7.70	9.80
Cd-Aspartate	4.40	8.00	10.24
Cd-Glutamate	4.48	8.02	10.33

Mixed systems :

The formation of three complexes $[Cd(MIDA)(\text{amino acid})]$, $[Cd(MIDA)(\text{amino acid})_2]$ and $[Cd(MIDA)_2(\text{amino acid})]$

Table 2(a). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-alaninate system

Alaninate = 0.01, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE									
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-10}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-12}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$ (calcd.)	ΔF (%)	
0.50	0.216	0.04029	1.68503	3.36865	6.97306	1.46	1.68	0.00	
1.00	0.226	0.05216	3.72546	3.72474	7.04748	1.47	3.72	0.00	
1.50	0.232	0.06904	6.13309	4.08825	7.12171	1.48	6.13	0.00	
2.00	0.236	0.09867	8.92051	4.45990	7.19950	1.50	8.91	-0.11	
2.50	0.239	0.13111	12.09595	4.83809	7.27238	1.49	12.09	0.00	
3.00	0.242	0.14381	15.67292	5.22407	7.34690	1.49	15.67	0.00	
3.50	0.244	0.17565	19.65757	5.61624	7.41784	1.48	19.65	0.00	
4.00	0.246	0.19701	24.06744	6.01668	7.49170	1.48	24.06	0.00	
4.50	0.248	0.21011	28.91145	6.42461	7.56580	1.48	28.91	0.00	
5.00	0.250	0.21653	34.20030	6.83991	7.63983	1.48	34.20	0.00	
A = 7126 (calcd.)		B = 3.02×10^{10}		C = 6.9×10^{12}		D = 1.48×10^{14}			

Table 2(b). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-alaninate system

Alaninate = 0.001, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE									
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-8}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-11}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$ (calcd.)	ΔF (%)	
0.50	0.166	0.01632	3.46050	6.91987	7.63975	1.48	3.46	0.00	
1.00	0.181	0.03809	11.48047	11.47990	8.37990	1.48	11.48	0.00	
1.50	0.191	0.04632	25.17039	16.77988	9.11992	1.48	25.17	0.00	
2.00	0.198	0.07112	45.55961	22.77952	9.83976	1.47	45.64	+0.19	
2.50	0.204	0.08215	73.99970	29.59965	10.59986	1.48	74.00	+0.01	
3.00	0.209	0.09224	111.08873	37.02938	11.30979	1.47	111.36	+0.25	
3.50	0.213	0.11792	160.11426	45.74676	12.18479	1.51	158.83	-0.79	
4.00	0.216	0.15118	217.52040	54.37995	12.81999	1.48	217.52	0.00	
4.50	0.219	0.17407	288.53600	64.11898	13.55977	1.48	288.54	+0.01	
5.00	0.221	0.21903	372.99241	74.59836	14.29967	1.48	373.00	+0.01	
A = 56.95 (calcd.)		B = 3.10×10^8		C = 6.9×10^{11}		D = 1.48×10^{14}			

Table 3(a). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-glycinate system

Glycinate = 0.01, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE									
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-10}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-12}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$ (calcd.)	ΔF (%)	
0.50	0.222	0.01209	2.50051	4.99874	8.57491	1.50	2.50	0.00	
1.00	0.232	0.01557	5.42263	5.42148	8.51485	1.48	5.43	+0.18	
1.50	0.238	0.2732	8.82226	5.88074	8.73830	1.59	8.82	0.00	
2.00	0.242	0.05121	12.66339	6.33112	8.80561	1.53	12.66	0.00	
2.50	0.245	0.07872	16.97735	6.79048	8.88193	1.53	16.97	0.00	
3.00	0.248	0.8698	21.77408	7.25764	8.95882	1.53	21.77	0.00	
3.50	0.250	0.11490	27.06449	7.73238	9.03539	1.53	27.06	0.00	
4.00	0.252	0.13263	32.86018	8.21475	9.11189	1.53	32.86	0.00	
4.50	0.254	0.14240	39.17238	8.704471	9.18826	1.53	39.17	0.00	
5.00	0.256	0.14576	46.01294	9.20235	9.26471	1.53	46.01	0.00	
A = 11451 (calcd.)		B = 4.57×10^{10}		C = 8.50×10^{12}		D = 1.53×10^{14}			

Table 3(b). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-glycinate system

Glycinate = 0.001, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE									
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-8}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-11}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$ (calcd.)	ΔF (%)	
0.50	0.169	0.034031	4.60192	9.20231	9.20462	1.41	4.60	0.00	
1.00	0.183	0.07298	14.50073	14.49996	9.89996	1.40	14.53	+0.20	
1.50	0.192	0.10144	30.85176	20.56732	10.64488	1.43	30.85	0.00	
2.00	0.199	0.11678	54.63991	27.31957	11.35978	1.43	54.64	+0.01	
2.50	0.205	0.11901	86.96810	34.78693	12.07477	1.43	86.96	0.00	
3.00	0.210	0.12358	128.90804	42.96908	12.78969	1.43	128.91	+0.01	
3.50	0.214	0.13918	181.53485	51.86687	13.50482	1.43	181.53	0.00	
4.00	0.218	0.14577	250.39751	62.59918	14.49979	1.50	245.92	-1.78	
4.50	0.221	0.15671	323.13203	71.80694	14.93487	1.43	323.13	0.00	
5.00	0.224	0.17386	422.99964	84.59977	15.99995	1.50	414.25	-2.06	
A = 27.25 (calcd.)		B = 4.60×10^8		C = 8.5×10^{11}		D = 1.43×10^{14}			

Table 4(a). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-aspartate system

Aspartate = 0.01, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE								
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-10}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-13}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{00} \times 10^{-7}$ (calcd.)	$\Delta F(\%)$
0.50	0.230	0.03037	4.81360	9.62365	1.00730	1.46	4.81	0.00
1.00	0.239	0.05436	10.13654	10.13477	1.01477	1.48	10.13	0.00
1.50	0.244	0.08579	15.98343	10.65443	1.02295	1.53	15.98	0.00
2.00	0.248	0.9860	22.36454	11.18138	1.03069	1.54	22.36	0.00
2.50	0.251	0.11598	29.29206	11.71611	1.03844	1.54	27.29	0.00
3.00	0.253	0.14827	36.77731	12.25851	1.04617	1.54	36.77	0.00
3.50	0.255	0.16773	44.83116	12.80839	1.05382	1.54	44.83	0.00
4.00	0.257	0.17769	53.46628	13.36612	1.06153	1.54	53.46	0.00
4.50	0.259	0.18030	62.69458	13.93173	1.06927	1.54	62.67	0.00
5.00	0.260	0.21029	72.52537	14.50472	1.07694	1.54	72.52	0.00
A = 17750 (calcd.)		B = 9.12×10^{10}		C = 1.0×10^{13}		D = 1.54×10^{14}		

Table 4(b). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-aspartate system

Aspartate = 0.001, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE								
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{00} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-8}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-12}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{00} \times 10^{-5}$ (calcd.)	$\Delta F(\%)$
0.50	0.176	0.01962	7.50135	14.99985	1.16996	1.40	7.50	0.00
1.00	0.189	0.04544	21.55112	21.54969	1.23996	1.40	21.57	+0.09
1.50	0.198	0.04871	43.26831	28.84458	1.31297	1.42	43.26	0.00
2.00	0.204	0.08016	73.66140	36.82998	1.38399	1.42	77.66	0.00
2.50	0.209	0.10276	113.81251	45.52443	1.45497	1.42	113.81	0.00
3.00	0.213	0.13608	166.95137	55.64998	1.54999	1.50	164.79	-1.29
3.50	0.217	0.13769	227.65647	65.04429	1.59597	1.42	227.65	0.00
4.00	0.220	0.16273	303.47995	75.86962	1.66799	1.42	303.48	+0.07
4.50	0.223	0.17554	393.32360	87.40492	1.73899	1.42	393.33	+0.01
5.00	0.226	0.17842	498.24162	99.64803	1.80996	1.42	498.25	+0.01
A = 143.50 (calcd.)		B = 9.15×10^8		C = 1.10×10^{12}		D = 1.42×10^{14}		

Table 5(a). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-glutamate system

Glutamate = 0.01, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE								
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-10}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-13}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-7}$ (calcd.)	$\Delta F(\%)$
0.50	0.231	0.04013	5.31496	10.62346	1.70691	1.38*	5.31	0.00
1.00	0.241	0.04216	11.48761	11.48438	1.71438	1.44	11.48	0.00
1.50	0.247	0.05027	18.53360	12.35358	1.72239	1.49	18.53	0.00
2.00	0.251	0.07187	26.46305	13.22991	1.72995	1.50	26.46	0.00
2.50	0.254	0.09700	35.28417	14.11237	1.73695	1.48	35.28	0.00
3.00	0.257	0.10294	45.01217	15.00298	1.74432	1.48	45.01	0.00
3.50	0.259	0.12859	55.65702	15.90108	1.75173	1.48	55.65	0.00
4.00	0.261	0.14409	67.22951	16.80657	1.75914	1.48	67.23	+0.01
4.50	0.263	0.15167	79.74069	17.71943	1.76654	1.48	79.74	0.00
5.00	0.265	0.15288	93.20302	18.63495	1.77399	1.48	93.20	0.00
A = 32301 (calcd.)		B = 9.77×10^{10}		C = 1.70×10^{13}		D = 1.48×10^{14}		*May be deleted.

Table 5(b). Data and results for cadmium-MIDA-glutamate system

Glutamate = 0.001, $E_{1/2}$ [M] = 0.580 vs SCE								
$[X] \times 10^3$	ΔE 1/2/V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-8}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-12}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$ (calcd.)	$\Delta F(\%)$
0.50	0.179	0.01450	9.32889	18.65463	1.77492	1.50	9.32	0.00
1.00	0.193	0.03039	28.28134	28.27976	1.84997	1.50	28.26	-0.07
1.50	0.202	0.04226	57.91161	38.60974	1.92198	1.48	57.91	0.00
2.00	0.209	0.04396	99.40082	49.69962	1.99598	1.48	99.40	0.00
2.50	0.214	0.06725	153.82609	61.52980	2.06999	1.48	153.82	0.00
3.00	0.218	0.09408	222.30020	74.09956	2.14398	1.48	222.30	0.00
3.50	0.222	0.09969	305.93559	87.40971	2.21799	1.48	305.93	0.00
4.00	0.226	0.12356	439.11675	109.77879	2.49996	2.00*	405.84	-7.57
4.50	0.228	0.14203	534.05994	118.67964	2.41999	1.60	523.12	-2.04
5.00	0.230	0.16672	658.90075	131.77983	2.43999	1.48	658.90	0.00
A = 157.50 (calcd.)		B = 9.78×10^8		C = 1.70×10^{12}		D = 1.48×10^{14}		*May be deleted.

acid)] would be expected. In these studies, on the mixed complex systems, a ligand displacement technique has been used in which a more complexing species is added to a mixture of a metal ion with weaker complexing species.

Table 6(a). Values of A, B, C and D for Cd-MIDA-amino acids systems

Amino acids concentration = 0.01 M				
Systems	A	B	C	D
Cd-MIDA-alaninate	7126	3.02×10^{10}	6.9×10^{12}	1.48×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-glycinate	11451	4.57×10^{10}	8.50×10^{12}	1.53×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-aspartate	17750	9.12×10^{10}	1.0×10^{13}	1.54×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-glutamate	32301	9.77×10^{10}	1.70×10^{13}	1.48×10^{14}

Table 6(b). Values of A, B, C and D for Cd-MIDA-amino acids systems

Amino acids concentration = 0.001 M				
Systems	A	B	C	D
Cd-MIDA-alaninate	56.95	3.10×10^8	6.9×10^{11}	1.48×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-glycinate	77.25	4.60×10^8	8.50×10^{11}	1.43×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-aspartate	143.50	9.15×10^8	1.10×10^{12}	1.42×10^{14}
Cd-MIDA-glutamate	157.50	9.78×10^8	1.70×10^{12}	1.48×10^{14}

The concentration of amino acids (weaker ligand) was held constant at 0.01 M and 0.001 M respectively and concentration of MIDA (stronger ligand) was varied over a wide range.

The F_{ij} functions were calculated by Schaap and McMasters treatment and the results are tabulated in Tables 2(a) to 5(b). The values of A, B, C and D at the two concentrations of amino acid ions for all the systems are tabulated in Tables 6(a) and 6(b). The overall stability constants β_{11} , β_{12} and β_{21} have been presented in Table 7.

Discussion

The tendency to add MIDA to Cd[X] and Cd[Y] (here [X] = MIDA and [Y] = amino acids) can be compared. The logarithm of stability constants of the above complexes are (3.24 and 5.69), (3.24 and 5.08), (3.24 and 4.98) and (3.24 and 4.65) for Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate systems respectively. The log values of stability constants for the addition of [Y] to Cd[X] and Cd[Y] are (4.12 and 3.30), (3.57 and 3.40), (3.57 and 3.60) and (3.32 and 3.54) for all the above systems respectively, indicating that the mixed ligand complexation is favoured. The log K values for addition of [X] to Cd[X]₂, Cd[XY] and Cd[Y]₂ are (5.12, 5.54 and 6.89), (5.12, 4.91 and 6.94), (5.12, 5.28 and 7.23), (5.12, 5.64 and 6.96) and (5.12, 6.10 and 6.97) all the under studying systems respectively and show that the addition of MIDA is preferred to amino acids.

Table 7. Stability constant of mixed ligand complexes of Cd-MIDA-amino acids systems

Systems	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Cd-MIDA-alaninate	9.93	14.48	14.84
Cd-MIDA-glycinate	9.38	14.66	14.93
Cd-MIDA-aspartate	9.38	14.96	15.02
Cd-MIDA-glutamate	9.13	14.99	15.23

Table 8. Values of mixing constant (log K_M) and stabilization constants (log K_S) for Cd-MIDA-amino acids systems

Sl. no.	Systems	log K_M	log K_S
1.	Cd-MIDA-alaninate	1.62	1.32
2.	Cd-MIDA-glycinate	0.99	0.69
3.	Cd-MIDA-aspartate	0.84	0.54
4.	Cd-MIDA-glutamate	0.59	0.29

The log K values for addition of [Y] to Cd[Y]₂, Cd[XY] and Cd[X]₂ are (2.14, 5.03 and 5.15), (2.10, 5.55 and 5.61), (2.24, 5.58 and 5.97), (2.31, 5.86 and 6.18) and (5.12, 6.10 and 6.97) for Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate systems respectively.

The values of β_{21} are higher than β_{30} so [Cd(X)₂Y] complexes are more stable than [Cd(X)₃] complexes. Simple and mixed complexes can be easily expressed by calculating the disproportionation constant K for the equilibria :

The values of log K_D is -0.60 statistically but the observed values are found to be (-3.27, -2.01, -1.71 and -1.19) for Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate systems respectively. More negative values of log K_D for each equilibrium account for the stability of mixed ligand complexes.

For comparing the stabilization of simple and mixed complexes, it is convenient to measure the mixing constants.

$$K_m = \frac{\beta_{11}}{\sqrt{(\beta_{02} \beta_{20})}} \quad (1)$$

and stabilization constants, as

$$\log K_S = \log K_m - \log 2 \quad (2)$$

The log K_m values are (1.62, 0.99, 0.84 and 0.59) and log K_S values are (1.32, 0.69, 0.54 and 0.29) for Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate systems respectively. These values are tabulated in Table 8. The positive values of mixing and stabilization constants indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes.

The tendency to form mixed ligand complexes in solution could be expressed quantitatively in other approach, compares the difference in stability $\Delta \log K$, which is the result from the subtraction of two constants, and must therefore, be a constant, this corresponds to :

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAB}^{MA} - \log K_{MB}^M \quad (3)$$

Since more coordination positions are available for bonding of the first ligand [A] to a given multivalent metal ion than for the second ligand [B].

$$\log K_{MA}^M > \log K_{MA_2}^{MA}$$

Usually holds, i.e. expects to observe negative values for $\Delta \log K$. Another probably more satisfactory manner is to determine statistical values for $\Delta \log K$. The statistical value for regular octahedron (oh) is 5/12 and $\Delta \log K_{oh} = -0.4$. For a square planer (sp) the value of $\Delta \log K_{sp} = -0.6$ and for the distorted octahedron (do) the statistical value i.e. $\Delta \log K_{do}$ lie between -0.9 and -0.3 .

The $\Delta \log K$ values can be obtained using the following equations :

$$\Delta \log X_{11} = \log \beta_{11} - (\log \beta_{10} + \log \beta_{01}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta \log X_{12} = \log \beta_{12} - (\log \beta_{10} + \log \beta_{02}) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \log X_{21} = \log \beta_{21} - (\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{01}) \quad (6)$$

The observed values of the $\Delta \log X_{11}$, $\Delta \log X_{12}$ and $\Delta \log X_{21}$ are $(-0.12, 1.13$ and $1.55)$, $(-0.73, 1.15$ and $1.58)$, $(-0.83, 1.15$ and $1.57)$ and $(-1.16, 1.16$ and $1.70)$ for systems Cd-MIDA-alaninate, Cd-MIDA-glycinate, Cd-MIDA-aspartate and Cd-MIDA-glutamate respectively.

The $\Delta \log K$ values are higher than the statistical values, which again prove that the ternary complexes are more stable than expected from statistical reasons.

Experimental

All chemicals (DL-alanine, DL-glycine, L-aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid and MIDA) were used as complexing agents. All above chemicals were AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. KNO_3 was used as supporting electrolyte. The ionic strength was maintained constant at $0.2 M$ with KNO_3 in all the systems studied in this chapter. $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ concentration of Cd^{II} was used in

the study. The temperature was maintained constant throughout the investigations at $303 \pm 1 K$. Experimental conditions are same as described earlier¹³.

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